

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**A RESEARCH STUDY TO ASCERTAIN THE RESTLESSNESS
FACTOR AMONG THE PATIENTS OF HEPATITIS C
INFECTION****Dr Saleha Javed, Dr Yasir Ashfaq, Dr Zainab Bibi**
Sheikh Zayed Hospital Rahim Yar Khan**Article Received:** January 2019**Accepted:** February 2019**Published:** March 2019**Abstract:**

Background: All around the globe, the health of people has suffered due to infection of hepatitis C. Experts are of the view that interferon therapy is not established, depression can be the outcome of Hepatitis C Infection.

Objective: The objective of the research was to determine the restlessness in patients of Hepatitis C.

Patients and Methods: The time duration of this research span from January 2017 to May 2017. The research was organized at Mayo Hospital, Lahore on a total of 100 patients including 42 male and 58 female patients. These patients were presented in the outdoor patients' department. These patients were positive for HCV and were not treated for the management of the disease. The interview was taken from these patients. Results were entered in a Performa and Hamilton Rating Scale for depression. SPSS was used for data assessment.

Results: 37.82 years was the mean age of all the participants. The number of patients found with depression, mild depression, moderate depression, severe depression and very severe depression was respectively 38%, 12%, 20%, 4% and 2%.

Conclusion: It is concluded by the results that non treated patients of hepatitis C were depressed. It also indicated that Hepatitis C may also cause depression among patients.

Keywords: Hepatitis C, Infection, Depression, Hamilton Rating Scale and Disease Management.

Corresponding author:**Saleha Javed,**
Sheikh Zayed Hospital Rahim Yar Khan

QR code

Please cite this article in press Saleha Javed et al., **A Research Study to Ascertain the Restlessness Factor Among the Patients of Hepatitis C Infection.**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(03).

INTRODUCTION:

The discovery of Hepatitis C is the most frequent blood-borne infection caused by a virus. All around the world, 180 million people are suffered from Hepatitis C. It is also the main reason for chronic liver disorder [1]. In some parts of Pakistan, the incidence of hepatitis C has been observed as 35% [2, 3]. According to experts' point of view, HCV infection and clinical restlessness are directly linked [1]. Interferon therapy is not available. Due to this, the occurrence of fatigue, co-morbid depression and cognitive decline is common [4]. As compared to the common pollution, the incidence of depression in the patients of HCV is high, according to DSM-IV criteria. In the common population, 6 – 10 percent people are found with depression. Whereas, the incidence of depression in patients of HCV is found in 24 to 70 percent of people [4].

Management of depressed HCV infected patients become easy and disability is reduced if depression is treated [5]. Otherwise, depression can result in fatigue and increased somatic complaints. Keeping in view the occurrence of depression among people, it should be taken seriously by patients and physicians. The objective of this research was to determine restlessness in patients of hepatitis C.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

The time duration of this research span from January 2017 to May 2017. The research was organized at Mayo Hospital, Lahore on a total of 100 patients including 42 male and 58 female patients. These patients were presented in the outdoor patients' department. These patients were selected from both the genders. The age limit of the participants was above thirteen years. An agreement was signed by all

the patients. On the basis of DSM-IV standard, depressive symptomatology and the comprehensive record were from all the pre-diagnosed HCV positive patients visiting the outdoor patient department and not receiving any treatment for Hepatitis C [6]. All the patients were interviewed and all the data was assembled on the Performa. Those were excluded from research who were with complex diabetes, heart failure, cirrhotic liver disorder, hepatic failure, hypothyroidism and renal failure. Patients indicated prior with HCV were selected for this research. They were not receiving any treatment. We determined the rate of depression in these patients. It is indicated by some researchers that depression results from some pathology of the virus itself. These patients were positive for HCV and were not treated for the management of the disease. The interview was taken from these patients. Results were entered in a Performa and Hamilton Rating Scale for depression [7]. SPSS was used for data assessment.

RESULTS:

37.82 years was the mean age of all the participants. The number of patients found with depression, mild depression, moderate depression, severe depression and very severe depression was respectively 38%, 12%, 20%, 4% and 2%. The number of males was 42 and the female was 58. Of these, 26 (44.82%) and 12 (28.5%) females and males were depressed respectively as far as sex differences are concerned in the prevalence of depression. Two patients (2%) thought of suicidal attempt. None of the patients was found with medication and mental healthcare provision for the management of depression. In the age group of 21 – 50 years, the incidence of depression was high. It is followed by 41 – 50 years (28%) and 21 – 40 years (22%).

Table – I: Gender Distribution

Gender (Percentage)	Normal	Depressed
Male	72	28
Female	56	44

Table – II: Level of Depression

Level of Depression	Frequency
Mild	12
Moderate	20
Normal	62
Severe	4
Very Severe	2
Total	100

Table – III: Distribution of Age Group

Age Group	Frequency
13 - 20 Years	4
21 - 30 Years	30
31 - 40 Years	22
41 - 50 Years	28
51 - 60 Years	14
61 - 65 Years	2
Total	100

DISCUSSION:

All around the globe including Pakistan, the health of people is affected by hepatitis C. It is also expected in the coming years. As compared to the common community, quality of life is affected and psychological indications are high commonly in patients with hepatitis C and other medical disorders [3]. Depression is also observed in these patients [8 – 10]. It was indicated in the study conducted by Elshahwi *et al.* that the percentage of patients untreated with IFN is 30% [9]. 28% and 35% was the limit of patients found with depression in previous research studies [11 – 13]. The occurrence of depression in our research was noticed in 38% of cases, which is comparable with other studies. Regardless of the presence of substance abuse or alcohol and IFN-alpha treatment, depression is a result of chronic hepatitis C [14]. Complications, doubts, incapability and changeable course of the disease as enteropathogenic factors found in this group [15]. In these patients, depression is mainly caused by the perception of stigma, changes in brain metabolites as evident by magnetic resonance imaging spectroscopy and emotional volatility [16].

CONCLUSION:

Based on the outcomes, it is concluded that depression is present in untreated patients of hepatitis C. It indicates virus itself cause of depression by disease pathology. In order to assess the relationship between depression and HCV, there is a need for a well-organized research study. To estimate the depression in time, psychiatric assessment is required at the start of therapy.

REFERENCES:

1. Golden J, O' Dwyer AM, Conroy RM. Depression and anxiety in patients with hepatitis C: prevalence, detection rates and risk factors. *Gen Hosp Psychiatry*. 2005; 27: 431 - 438.
2. Carta MG, Hardy MC, Garofalo A, Pisano E, Nonni V, Intilla G, *et al.* Association of chronic hepatitis C with major depressive disorders: irrespective of interferon-alpha therapy. *Clin Pract Epidemiol Ment Health* 2007 Oct. 23; 3: 22.
3. Grassi L, Satriano J, Serra A, Binacosino B, Zotos S, Sighinolfi L, Ghincli F. Emotional stress, psychosocial variables and coping associated with hepatitis C virus and human immunodeficiency virus infections in intravenous drug use. *Psychotic Psychosom* 2002; 71:342-349.
4. Forton DM, Hamilton G, Allsop JM, Grover VP, Wesnes K, O' Sullivan C, *et al.* Cerebral immune activation in chronic hepatitis C infection: a magnetic resonance spectroscopy study. *J Hepatol* 2008; 49:316-322.
5. Janks EA, Me Graw S, Garcia-Tsao G, Fraenkel L. Psychosocial issues in hepatitis C: a qualitative analysis. *Psychosomatics* 2008; 49:494-501.
6. El- Zayadi A. Hepatitis C co-morbidities affecting the course and response to therapy. *World Gastroenterol* 2009; 15:4993-9.
7. Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders. 4, h ed (TR). Washington D.C.; American Psychiatric Association, 1994; pp 445-69.
8. Hamilton M. A rating scale for depression. *J Neur Psych* 1960,23:56-62.

9. Forton DM, Allsop JM, Main J, Foster GR, Thomas HC, Taylor Robinson SD. Evidence for a cerebral effect of hepatitis C virus. *Lancet* 2001; 358:38-39.
10. Elshahawi, Ilcaba H, Hussein, Mobarak M, Allam, Ensa A. Depression Comorbidity in patients with Chronic hepatitis C and its possible relation to treatment outcome. *Middle East Current Psychiatry* 2011; 18 (I)-p23-28.
11. Yawn BP, Rocca LG, Wollan PC. 10-year trends in the diagnosis and treatment of hepatitis C and concomitant mental health disorders: 1995 to 2005. *Prime Care Companion J Clin Psychiatry*. 2008; 10: 349- 354.
12. Libman H, Richard S, David N, Debbie MC, Jessica MR, John V, Julie KA et al. Hepatitis C infection is associated with depressive symptoms in HIV infected adults with alcohol problems. *A Joun Gastro* 2006. 101, 1804- 1810.
13. "Why Depression is Likely with Hepatitis C", by Nicole Cutler, L.Ac. Posted by Editors at January 19, 2009.
14. Khattak MF, Salamat N, Bhatti F.A, Qureshi TZ. Scro prevalence of hepatitis B, C and HIV in blood donors in Northern Pakistan. *J Pak Med Assoc* 2002; 52: 398- 402.
15. Aziz S, Memon A, Tilly HI, Rasheed K, Jehangir K, Quraishy MS. Prevalence of HIV, hepatitis B and C amongst health workers of Civil Hospital Karachi. *J Pak Med Assoc* 2002; 52:92-4.
16. Raison CL, Demetrashvili M, Capuron L, Miller AH. Neuropsychiatric adverse effects of interferon-alpha: recognition and management. *CNS Drugs* 2005; 19: 105- 123.
17. Sockalingam S, Blank D, A1 Jarad A, Alosaimi F, Hirschfield G, Abbey SE; A comparison of depression screening Instruments in hepatitis C symptoms; *Psychosomatics* 52 (5), 433-40.